

Shift to sustainable energy and the need for it

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अन्नान्द्रवन्ति भूतानि पर्जन्यादन्नसम्भवः ।

यज्ञान्द्रवति पर्जन्यो यज्ञः कर्मसमुद्भवः ।

- Shreemad Bhagavad Geeta (Chapter 3 Verse 14)

Zoya left from Kerala to study at prestigious St. Stephen's College, Delhi. This was her first visit to the capital of India. Just after reaching NCR, she experienced some trouble in breathing and irritation in her eyes. She recalled the good old clean air and green environment of her hometown. Thought came to her, and she asked herself this question, what would be the solution to this anthropogenic environmental crisis. She recalled the word 'sustainability' from her last discussion with her friends. She started writing an essay, starting with pondering upon the idea of sustainability, its evolution, and sustainable energy. Later she focussed on its need and, various national and international efforts for shift towards sustainable energy.

The idea of sustainability first emerged in a meeting organized by Club of Rome. Where, economic growth in sustainable way was emphasized owing to depleting resources; increasing oil prices; and increasing inequality in economic growth among the countries across the world. During 1970s, following the Club of Rome conference, a conclusion was reached that economic growth cannot continue indefinitely due to rapid resource depletion. Thus, global commitments were required to limit economic growth to certain level and redistribute wealth among countries for poverty alleviation.

Soon the definition for sustainability got further refined as the time progressed. Environment, economy and society become integral part of the sustainability. Sustainability can be defined as comprehensive growth in the physical and environment resource-constrained world where humans are the part of the environment not the only recipient. Sustainable growth implies that we take into consideration the future generations as well.

For the progress of any human civilization, energy is required to carry out day-to-day activities. Energy is required for growing food, manufacturing goods, and meeting basic human amenities. Subsequent sections will discuss about the

concept of sustainable energy and the need for sustainable energy in a multi-dimensional approach.

SUSTAINABLE ENERGY

As on today, majority of the countries exploit conventional and fossil fuel-based energy, like coal, gas, oil, wood, nuclear, for its economic and societal growth. These conventional sources are depleting and causing huge damage to the environment. Thus, concept like renewable energy and sustainable energy emerged. Renewable energy is energy obtained from sources which renew themselves and does not deplete over the years. But renewable energy like solar, wind, hydro, tidal, geothermal, etc. are dependent on external factors which raises question on its reliability. Flexibility and availability of energy using renewable sources throughout the day is difficult to achieve. Thus, the concept of sustainable energy emerges. Sustainable energy does not emphasize on complete shift from conventional source to renewable sources. Sustainable energy is the energy derived from sources which can be used to meet current energy demand without hindering existing operation and energy needs. Sustainable energy sources are sources which takes into consideration depleting resources, energy need and future generation's climate and environment. Renewable energy sources could be labelled as sustainable if they are available in plenty to meet current energy requirement.

NEED

Climate change is the major concern which demands for shift to sustainable energy. Due to climate change, events like global warming, heatwaves, frequent floods, extreme weather, incessant rains, flash floods, tornadoes, hurricane, forest fires, etc. are occurring more frequently and with large severity compared to last century. We reached at this stage due to indiscriminate use of conventional fossil-based fuels and unsustainable practices in the past.

Climate change and man-made environment interact with each other. Windstorm and prolonged winters are causing air pollution and sustenance of it. Air pollution further get accumulated due to transport and industrial emissions, plastic burning and paddy stubble burning. Smog and depreciating air quality index (AQI) in New Delhi is one such example. Air pollution is at hazardous level in major cities in India. Air pollution is dangerous for all age groups right from infants to old age people. This also give rise to poor visibility leading to road accidents and disruptions in normal operation. Transport, educational institute, industrial activities are curtailed during extremely poor AQI, leading to huge economic loss.

Speaking of geographical environment, impact on *biodiversity* can't be neglected. Climate change is leading to damage to biodiversity and ecology. Migrating bird's patterns have changed, causing extinction of various plant species in the path earlier followed by migrating birds. Floods and deforestation have caused migration of various animal species unbalancing biodiversity of the area. Only way to deal with challenges, emerged mainly due to climate change, is to shift towards sustainable energy ASAP.

We have discussed about life on land, let's focus our attention for a while to life in water. Oil is extracted either from land or sea floor. Oil extracted from land is transported to energy demand centres. Run-off of the leaked oil in rivers and nearby ponds/lakes destroy the living species in these water bodies. Oil is transported through large ship to various countries. We often hear the news of leakage of tons of oil in ocean. This heavily impacts *marine life* existing in the ocean. Such oil spillage ends up by the coastal region too, damaging beaches and *coastal reef*. This harm the *tourism* industry in India as well.

Coming back to land, *transportation* vehicles use petroleum oil and natural gas-based fuels. These vehicles emit oil particulate matters through gas nozzles or sometimes have oil leakages in pipes and engines. During rain, the oil run-off from the road and mixes either with groundwater or nearby rivers or ponds. Leading to harmful and prolonged effect on health of both human and marine life.

Particulate matter of harmful gas emitted by vehicles and industries, like sulphur dioxide, and oil particulate particles also lead to acid rain. Acid rain causes loss of soil fertility, damaging plant life, biodiversity loss, desertification, etc. *Land* becomes barren, unusable for agriculture purposes. Climate change is also major cause for degradation of soil quality. Lack of trees on land, mainly due to deforestation, lead to soil erosion further permanently changing land-use pattern. And the cycle continues.

Damage to agricultural land leads to drop in its productivity and output. Shortage of *food* and rise in crop price leads to malnutrition. Shunting and waisting are common phenomena present in various developing countries. Shortage of food also lead to inflationary prices. This causes *economic divide* among society. Food shortage impacts human health among poor and marginalized people. This leads to loss of productive man/woman hours. When the bread earner is unhealthy, family deals with extreme *poverty*. Poor agriculture productivity may cause job loss of men and women in the rural areas. It is a well-known fact that majority of agricultural laborers in rural area

are women. Lack of source of income for woman may further hinder their personal growth and well-being.

To deal with shortage of food, fertilizer is used for agricultural production. Fertilizer and pesticide contain harmful chemicals. Production of crop using fertilizer is considered as unsustainable farming as it causes damage to soil. Crop produced using fertilizer contains carcinogenic substance in it. This causes cancer in humans. Run-off of fertilizer in nearby water bodies is not good for marine life as well. It is important to strike a *balance* between food shortage and fertilizer usage. Not just sustainable energy but also sustainable farming needs to be promoted. Complete ban on fertilizer in farming was one of the reasons behind recent Sri Lanka's economic crisis. Thus, importance of a sustainable path is immeasurable.

Food and water are basic human needs. After covering food, let's discuss about *water*. Firstly, about the extraction of conventional fossil fuel. Extraction of coal, oil and gas requires huge amount of water to keep the machines, mainly drillers, cool. Water is used to form steam which is required to run mainly extraction machinery. After extraction, water is consumed for washing purpose, coal washery is one such example. To convert this conventional fuel-based energy to useful electrical energy, again, steam is required. Water intensity to convert conventional fuel-based energy is higher as compared to renewable sources.

Let's look at *economic* aspect regarding need to shift from conventional to sustainable energy. Majority of energy needs of India is met by coal, oil, and natural gas. India imports 90% of its total crude oil demand. Recently, during summers, due to huge electricity demand – India was forced to import coal due to coal shortages. Such imports lead to economic cost and outflow of funds. India must pay huge sums of money owing to price fluctuation of oil in international market. US, Russia and OPEC countries hoard oil to artificially increase oil prices which drains financial capital of our country.

Such reliance on imports from other countries is dangerous to *India's energy security*. As recently witness global supply chain disturbance due to Suez Canal blockade, COVID-19 pandemic, and Ukraine-Russia war. Such disturbance may lead to failure to meet energy demand of India. To protect energy security, India must shift towards other sustainable energy source and decrease her dependency on energy import.

If India can become self-reliant to meet its energy need then it will help in protecting her *geo-political interests* as well. As we can learn from the

experience of European countries in Ukraine-Russia war, who rely on Russia for energy need, are funding war against themselves.

Import of petroleum oil and natural gas makes them costly. To pay for these, Union, and State Governments charges *taxes* in form of VAT. These taxes are currently at Rs. 50/litre which is 40-50% of total fuel price. Higher taxes on petrol and diesel lead to higher transportation cost. Food prices and manufactured goods price increase leading to *inflation* and slowing down economic growth. It is a well-established theory that taxes causes dead-weight loss to society.

Growing population requires more energy. If India could come up with local sustainable energy sources, then it may help not only in huge saving of economic cost but also generate *livelihood* opportunities in India. Alternative sustainable energy initiatives in India can lessen unemployment in our country. Technology required to generate energy from sustainable sources can promote local employment. Amount paid to oil exporting countries can be invested in R&D for sustainable energy technology.

Now it's time focus our attention to another important aspect of any human civilization i.e., *art, culture and heritage*. We have already witnessed yellowing of Taj Mahal, mainly due to air pollution. Every year, Yamuna River, which is used for worshipping by women during Chhath, frosts with toxic foam. Recently, Kali Bein River, a spiritual site for Sikh community, was in news for polluted water. All these are example of water pollution caused by oil and chemicals either to convert conventional energy to useful energy or leakages in the system. Extreme heatwaves and incessant rainfall have hampered 'Nukaad Nataks' and 'Open theatre events'. COVID-19 pandemic, caused by unsustainable practices like eating wildlife animals, impacted income of various artists working in theatres and live events. Lest we forget that extreme weather events are damaging historical architecture sites of our country. Heritage sites located on coastal area soon to be flooded if we don't mitigate climate change. Erosion of cultural heritage site like UNESCO Hampi or Konark Sun Temple can lead to reduction in tourism.

India is dealing with various *disasters* on numerous fronts. Typhoons originating from Bay of Bengal have become a common occurrence. People often become homeless due to such travesty. Floods in Manipur, Bihar, Kerala, Tamil Nadu, Uttarakhand has shown the outcome of interference with nature. In current year we have experienced heatwaves in major part of the country. As on today, monsoon precipitation this year is 8% less than the previous year. All these events can be linked to climate change. If human beings had adopted

sustainable means earlier, then huge loss of life could have been averted. We still have time; it is predicted that if global warming continues to rise as usual then coastal areas of India will submerge into water.

In many instances, we discussed various issues and disaster occurring due to climate change and traditional conventional energy. Shift to sustainable energy will not only help in mitigating climate change and improve our environment but also make us 'Aatma-Nirbhar' in the field of energy such that whenever disaster or global supply chain disruption would occur; India will continue to grow without any hinderance. Let us talk about various way in shifting to sustainable energy, corresponding India's, and global community in sustainable pathway.

SHIFT

During 1980s, holes began appearing in the ozone layer of the atmosphere. Scientist were concern about it due to lethal nature of UV radiation on skin. They found out root cause behind this phenomenon; it was chlorofluorocarbons (CFC). In this regard, global commitments were made to ban manufacturing and usage of CFCs. Soon after, just within two decades, ozone layer healing started. This is one of the successful case studies which shows that environment and nature will heal itself if humans avoid indiscriminate use of resources.

Like above case, the main root cause of climate change is identified to be rising carbon dioxide and greenhouse gases (GHG) emission. We must cut down our CO₂ and GHG emission to avert climate change. One way to avoid it is by shift towards renewable energy in sustainable manner.

Solar Energy is one of the most abundant and clean energy. Energy from solar insolation is converted using photovoltaic (PV) panel into electrical and other useful energy. Daylight and clear sky are required for optimal generation of electricity. During night hours or cloudy weather, generation would be almost none. To make solar energy more sustainable, battery storage and pumped storage could be used. Government of India recently announced an innovative initiative with the International Solar Alliance to create One Sun – One World – One Grid (OSOWOG). This will avert challenges like peak electricity demand during night hours as sun never sets in any one part of the world. Government of India has launched series of productive linked incentives for solar and battery manufacturing. This solves the problem of environmental pollution, energy security and unemployment. To make solar energy as sustainable energy, optimal location with highest solar insolation for setting up the plant using ISRO's VEDAS portal.

In addition, sunlight heats up the air, land and sea creating low-pressure and high-pressure zone for wind currents, giving birth to another form of renewable energy commonly known as Wind Energy. Unlike solar, wind energy is available throughout 24 hours but bound to a condition that wind flows above certain threshold. Frequent changes in wind speed and wind direction could result in variability in electricity generation from wind power. Conversion of wind energy in sustainable energy could be done by placing wind power plants at the site with abundant and steady wind flow. Help of ISRO and India Meteorological Department (IMD) to be taken before selecting the site for wind project. Off-shore wind power plants should be preferred as wind current above sea is streamlined whereas wind power is lost on land due to uneven surface and man-made construction. To safeguard interest of wind power projects and its sustainability, MNRE issued order to abolish the practice of reverse auctioning in binding of these projects. Battery storage and pumped storage solutions are also applicable in wind as well.

Evaporation of water due to sunlight; and cooling of these water vapour due to wind, leads to glacier formation in mountainous region and rain in plateau region, giving rise to another renewable energy known as Hydro Energy. In India, hydro projects below 25 MW capacity are term as small hydro project whereas 25 MW or more capacity is termed as large hydro projects. Only the small hydro projects are accounted in renewable energy. Hydro power projects are more flexible and reliable than solar and wind projects. Government of India launched National Hydro Energy Mission (NHEM) for promotion of hydro energy.

Water is used for agricultural purposes. One such by-product of agricultural activity is Bioenergy. Bioenergy consists of Biomass, Biogas and Biofuels. Electricity is generated from bagasse in biomass project. Biomass is carbon-neutral and helpful to boost economic activities in rural area. Government of India provides capital subsidy for such projects. In biogas plants, using Anaerobic Digestion (A.D.) waste is converted to gases like CH_4 , H_2S and CO_2 . This gas is then converted into useful energy. Government of India launched New National Biogas and Organic Manure Programme (NNBOMP) for promoting its use. Biofuel is third type of bioenergy where genetically modified crops are grown, like sugarcane, corn, etc. These crops are used for generation of biofuel like biodiesel or ethanol. Biofuels are mostly applicable in transport sector and reduces CO_2 emission. In 2021, Government of India launched National Policy on Biofuels for its promotion and use. Bioenergy can be a sustainable energy only if large number of small cluster projects are promoted across the country.

There is another form of energy which could be used in urban areas. These projects are called as Waste-to-Energy (WTE) power plants. In such projects, municipal waste collected from different sources and processed before feeding it to burner. Steam generated in boiler is either used for industrial processes or for electricity generation. Various municipal corporations are setting up WTE plants by raising 'Green Bonds' in capital market. Ghaziabad Municipal Corporation was the first one to issue green bonds for environment and climate change purpose. Government of India, under the aegis of Swachh Bharat Abhiyan has promoted for segregation of waste at the source. Segregated waste is easy to process and can be easily employed for WTE.

To meet India's energy need, these renewable energy forms could be sustainable with additional efforts. One such way is promotion of distributed renewable energy (DRE) system and micro-grid. Promotion and utilization of renewable energy at its source is a great way to make it sustainable. It also helps in reducing transmission losses. Government of India is constantly promoting for rooftop solar and net-metering. Using net-metering, individual rooftop solar plant is connected to grid. Owner of these plants can sell excess of electricity to distribution companies. In addition, inter-connecting various renewable energy sources (RES) with small micro-grid can help in meeting energy requirements of small regions. As Gandhiji vocalized for village economy and Panchayati Raj system, similarly, aligned with same principle a village can set up its own micro-grid to meet its demand and become self-reliant. Micro-grid enables market trading of electricity in a small area which can lead to reduction in prices of electricity.

Sustainable use of any form of energy is beneficial to society than rampant usage. This brings us to the main way to promote sustainable energy i.e., lifestyle. Although India has very low per capita emission yet there is wide scope for improvement in sustainable use of energy. During COP26 in Glasgow, Prime Minister Narendra Modi gave a mantra for sustainability which is "LiFE – Lifestyle for Environment". Unless every citizen across the world doesn't adopt this mantra, we won't be able to give clean, green, and sustainable environment for our future generation. Energy conservation and energy saving lifestyle should be adopted. Simple things like segregating dry and wet waste in different dustbins. Using bicycle for short distances commute. Travelling through public transport system instead of individual car. Buying BEE 5-star energy rated devices for personal use. Avoiding single use plastic in daily usage and requesting for paper bags from the shopkeeper or carrying our own plastic bag in pocket. Keeping air conditioner on 24° Celsius and many more. Avoiding meat-based food products and adopt vegetarian diet. These are some of the

lifestyles we can adopt to save energy. Lifestyle changes can be summed up by famous quote by Mahatma Gandhiji - "Be the change you wish to see in the world".

Government of India and various State Governments are constantly striving for cleaner and greener environment. Climate change is one of the top agenda for the government. Union Government has launched "National Action Plan for Climate Change". India is also aligned in meeting its Nationally Determined Contributions (NDCs). India is balancing its economic growth and development alongside promoting cleaner and greener energy. In COP26, India gave itself new targets for net-zero by 2070, 500GW of generation from renewable sources, LiFE, etc. India has long and tough way to go. Transfer of renewable technology and availability of different sources of fund is crucial to meet these targets. These measures need to be supported by Climate Finance of US\$100 billion agreed by developed countries in COP 16 in the year 2010. India still awaits on these promises. *Global efforts* are on the way as India has signed various bilateral and multilateral treaties to deal with climate change. All countries are doing the best of their abilities and interest. But we need to remember the quote from Swami Vivekananda, "Do not wait for anybody or anything. Do whatever you can, build your hope on none". India must adopt sustainable energy and practices in each walk of life.

Zoya's face lightened up, and she felt enlightened when is recalled Verse 14 of Chapter 3 in Shreemad Bhagavad Geeta. Now she understood the true meaning of the verse "Life sustains due to food; food comes from rain. Rain comes after performing sacrifice and sacrifice is outcome of performing prescribed duty". Her eyes were filled new hope and determination. She wanted a changed environment, but she realised that government, private entities, inter-governmental organization, civil societies, etc. are doing their job. She must also do her prescribed duty – adopting a sustainable LiFE.

-The End-

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